

Do Venture Capital Firms Spur Innovation: Investigating Venture Capital Firm's Portfolio Companies in Karachi, Pakistan

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The significance of venture capital in spurring innovation for venture backed entrepreneurial startups has been majorly emphasized in the literature. However, different processes or central theme for exploring the role of venture capitalists were identified and used. This research study is going to highlight the factors affecting the innovation process of the startups. In other words, the impact of innovation input by venture capitalist is on the innovation output of the portfolio firm investigated. This research study gathered the data from the founders of the venture backed startups and assumed that the role of venture capital and innovation is positively and significantly related. In order to validate this relationship, the participants were offered for a semi-structured interview based on 20 open-ended questions. In addition, by applying Thematic Analysis, this relationship is evaluated and examined. It has been concluded that the VC plays a significant and positive role in spurring innovation. Venture Capitalists add value to the company by playing a far more active role in helping businesses expand by providing additional competencies, contacts, expertise, and several more value-added services. The findings and conclusions of this research study would enable the entrepreneurial startups to recognize the importance, advantages, and the contribution of the VCs in fostering innovation for their new and risky startups.

Keywords: VENTURE CAPITAL, START-UPS, INNOVATION, ENTREPRENEURSHIP, VENTURE BACKED FIRMS

1. Introduction

Venture Capital is the capital investment in a firm and other facilities are also provided i.e. guidance, expertise, industry connection etc. Venture Capitalist participates in the firm's decision-making process because they become the equity owners of the firm after investment is made. [Potterie \(2004\)](#) defines venture

capital as a financial intermediary which finances young and small innovative start-ups which have high growth potential and high uncertainty. Furthermore, [Edgar \(1995\)](#) described Venture Capital as its value is more than financing, through venture capital investment investees get monitoring and counseling services as well which helps investees to get higher return, lower risk and lower operational costs.

Venture Capitalists (VCs) are now seen as crucial players in well-integrated systems of innovation ([Cooke et al., 1997](#); [Powell et al., 2002](#); [Kenney, 2011](#)). The role of venture capital investment fostering innovation has become the most discussed topic between academia and policy makers. Mostly, startups come with an innovative idea which is convertible into a product, but startups face different barriers in finding finance to make it happen, venture capitalists particularly are well suited to finance and monitor innovative startups ([Faria & Barbosa 2014](#)). Governments have made policies to promote venture capital activities to support innovation and growth worldwide [Lerner \(1995\)](#), as it plays a significant part in the development of many sectors in different economies. There is a need of active venture capital investments in any emerging economies to promote innovation, technology and entrepreneurial growth ([Imamuddin, 2009](#)).

The Venture Capital Industry in Pakistan is gradually increasing its growth rate seeding the early & growth stage venture capital firm. There are several venture capital firms in Pakistan which are dedicated to raise venture capital funds such as, Sarmayacar, i2i Ventures, TPL e-Ventures and many more. But also many venture capital firms in Pakistan are facing different problems, running in infancy because of risk adverse attitude of entrepreneurs, limited support from the government and listing regulations for SMEs and family owned business mindset. The purpose of this research is to find an evidence whether the activities of VCs do spur innovation or not. To find this evidence the Venture Capital Investment Companies of Pakistan has been studied in supporting continuous innovation in venture capital investment company's portfolio start-ups. The main purpose of this study is therefore to present some indication of research in this field in Pakistan. The developing country must grasp the relevance not only in the context of the particular VC industry but also in the national framework of the rapid growth of start-ups. Looking into the aforesaid facts, the current research was designed to examine the role of Venture Capitalists in fostering innovation in Karachi, Pakistan.

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between venture capitalists and innovative start-ups, whether venture capitalists do matter in persistence of innovation within start-ups activities of the entrepreneurs.

- To investigate Venture Capital Firms really spur innovation
- To identify the importance of Venture Capital Firms for start-ups in Pakistan
- To observe whether Venture Capitalist in Pakistan really provide managerial expertise, guidance, Industry connections to firms or not
- To draw conclusions and recommendations especially for new startup firms, entrepreneurs and venture capital firms.

This study will play a vital role for new start-ups while choosing financial intermediary for initial and later investment, entrepreneurs will come to know the results of venture capital investment companies within

Pakistan whether they are promoting innovation or not. Furthermore, this study help ventures capitalists to find gaps to fill and opportunities to catch. There is a need of active venture capital investments in any emerging economies like Pakistan to promote innovation, technology and entrepreneurial growth. Innovative start-ups are backbone of a country, this study help government to know about current venture capitalist's role and relationship with new start-ups. The study has significance because no similar study was carried out to before, for role of VCs fostering innovation especially in Karachi, Pakistan, and therefore the influencing variables behind effective venture capital funding can be recognized by doing such a study. The growth rate of the VC industry in Pakistan could be improved if investing in specified elements, therefore achieving national development goals in the industry concerned.

2. Literature Review

According to [Gompers and Lerner \(2001\)](#), three elements contribute to VC funding's favorable impact on innovation: (1) a more efficient and effective screening industry; (2) venture firms' counsel to entrepreneurs, as well as post-investment monitoring and control; and (3) investment staging. These variables, they believe, explain why VC investment has a much greater influence on innovation than the conventional R&D. [Hirukawa and Ueda \(2008\)](#), on the other hand, utilized total factor productivity as a measure of innovation. They discover that total factor productivity growth is frequently positively and strongly connected to future VC investment, implying that the introduction of a new technology raises demand for VC rather than VC driving innovation.

In contrast to [Hirukawa and Ueda \(2008\)](#), [Gonzalez-\(2013\)](#) Uribe's research backs up [Kortum and Lerner's \(2001\)](#) findings that VC funding enhances the scale of a company's inventive activity. Furthermore, [Bernstein, Giroud & Townsend \(2016\)](#) examine venture capitalists' involvement in fostering innovation within portfolio businesses. Even if VC-backed start-ups tend to be more innovative than others, it is not clear whether this is because of the selection, as investment objectives, of especially innovative enterprises ("screening" or "selection effect"). Or because on-site involving venture capitalists enables portfolio firms to become more innovative ("control" or "treatment effect").

[Moirangthem, N. S., & Nag, B. \(2021\)](#) demonstrated the value of venture capital to startups in his study where VCs appeared to play a big role in supplying money to companies, owing to their extensive network and experience. The case study investigates how venture capitalists became involved with a company and infuse their value-added operations. To support the firm's overall expansion, the entrepreneurs should positively and successfully take those initiatives from the VCs. As well as, new ideas, monitoring financial performance, monitoring non-financial performance, development of new strategies, crisis management, assisting merger and acquisition, seeking additional finance, introduction to new customers and suppliers, recruitment of staff and top management, technology platform, marketing and networking, operations planning, and other value-added activities of VCs were also discovered ([Kumar, 2015](#)).

Furthermore, [Caleffi, I. \(2021\)](#) has explored the phenomena of venture capital (VC) and how it can be used to keep up with innovation and create value within a company. The value development process for the VC was

examined in this study, from portfolio formation to Open Innovation application, as well as value generation for the target firm. When the individual elements of the index as well as the composite impact of venture capital on innovation are examined, the findings reveal that venture capital investment strongly spurs innovation. These findings encourage governments and policymakers to foster innovation by allowing venture capital investment, which provides an alternative source of money for firms that are unable to acquire cash through traditional fund markets (Khan, et al., 2021).

The most supported position, however, is that venture capital investors are "business builders" which both drive innovation and professionalization and marketing techniques. Based on Holmstrom & Tirole's double moral hazard model (1997) of venture capital, this theory underlines the active involvement of the venture capitalists as coaches and monitors of novice entrepreneurs (Baker & Gompers, 2003). In order to establish successful commercial operations, venture investors would consequently supply financing to teams of entrepreneurs as well as non-financial services such as monitoring, assistance and guidance. Venture capital (VC) plays a demonstrable role in fostering innovation, economically (Aizenman & Kendall 2012; Caselli, Gatti & Perrini 2009; Colombo, Dawid & Kabus 2012; Füss, & Schweizer 2012; Hasan & Wang 2006; Hirukawa & Ueda 2011; Keuschnigg, 2004; Popov & Roosenboom 2012; Zhang et al., 2013). In general, financial support is provided to innovative startup companies when necessary, as well as to increase portfolio companies' design, development and performance (Berger & Schaeck 2011; Carvell et al., 2013; Cumming, 2010; De Clercq et al., 2006; Faria & Barbosa; Gompers & Lerner, 2001; Hellmann & Puri, 2002; Lahr & Mina, 2016; Liao et al. 2016; Liao et al. 2014; Ning et al. 2015; Schwienbacher 2014).

In recent years the relationship between venture capital, innovation and economic development has become increasingly attentive to both academics and political leaders (Bottazzi & Da Rin, 2002; Da Rin, 2016; Obrimah, 2016). However, this research is specifically focused on the relationship between venture capital and innovation and does VC really foster innovation particularly in Pakistan. The specification is mostly due to the fact that venture capital could be considered as a major source or driver for innovation, especially in a developing country like Pakistan.

3. Conceptual Framework

Venture capital creates value, because (a) it increases financial resources of companies and (b) it often acts as coaches of the companies (Hellmann, 2000), supporting companies with both financial resources and other resources, such as management experience, access to informal networks and professional business models. Hirukawa and Ueda (2011) develop two distinct hypotheses on the basis of this conceptual background: the "venture capital first hypothesis" and the "innovation first hypothesis". While the second hypothesis concentrates on the selection effect, assuming innovation induces investing venture capital, the first hypothesis concerns value-generating functions, as long as venture capital promotes innovation. Here, we focus on the impact of venture capital on the innovation performance of the portfolio companies. This research is mainly focused on the "venture capital first" theory and investigates the direct effect of VCs on innovations.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

Due to the difficulty of the innovation process characterized by numerous phases, from core research to market penetration with new goods, a single measure of innovation method can overcome critical connections and produce non-robust results (Kleinknecht, Van Montfort, & Brouwer, 2002). Therefore, i) introducing new products, ii) introducing substantially modified products and iii) introducing new or modified items will be measured in this study as the innovation output. However, i) finance, ii) guidance/mentoring, iii) industry connection, and iv) management expertise would be taken as measures of innovation input by the venture capitalists to the portfolio firms. The conceptual framework is drawn above depicting inputs by VCs to portfolio firms and innovation outputs by portfolio firms.

4. Research methodology

A. Research paradigm

This study used anti-positivism or interpretivist as a research methodology. Interpreters believe that individual experiences' personal interpretations may be interpreted; However, positivists believe that culture may be evaluated objectively using scientific principles such as closely watching, learning and examining the ability and knowledge. Results are formed by interactions between researchers and participants; research is also made by examining person's own opinions and ideas rather than the facts that can be proved.

B. Research approach & design

This proposed research will use a primary qualitative research methodology. Qualitative research relies on information from first-hand observation, interviews, surveys, focus groups, participant observation, and other sources. The research has been conducted to determine the influence of venture capitalist firms in

entrepreneurial endeavors. The study's major goal is to identify the factors that contribute in fostering innovation by venture capital firms. The independent variables of this study are the innovation inputs by venture capitalists i.e. finance, guidance, industry connections, management expertise and how they are influencing and fostering innovation.

C. Sample size and technique

The technique of picking informants depending on their capacity to describe a given topic, concept, or subject is known as purposive sampling. In this situation, in order to construct a 'criterion-based' purposive sample, only those respondents who match the investigation's criteria has been chosen. The study's sample size is made up of seven people who were interviewed to find out the answers to the research questions.

D. Research instrument

A semi-structured interview strategy was used in this research. The respondents were asked 20 open-ended questions in this study, which encouraged dialogue with the interviewee.

E. Data collection

The data for this research study was gathered through semi-structured interviews. The respondents for this study were CEOs, founders, and managers, and an acceptable number of respondents were chosen as the sample. This involved interviewing approximately 7 people for the study's purposes.

F. Data analysis

A qualitative data analysis approach was used to analyze it. A form of qualitative data analysis is thematic analysis.

Thematic analysis is a tool for conducting qualitative research. It's also used for a wide range of texts, including interview transcripts.

Fig. 2: Steps in Thematic Analysis

Rather than adopting a standard coding scheme, this study took the method of looking for similarities & contradictions and then creating codes and themes from them.

Fig. 3: Steps of Thematic Analysis Followed in this Study

Step 1: Familiarization

Data familiarity is a method of immersing and familiarizing oneself with data acquired in semi-structured interview sessions. For the interviews and discussion sessions, audio was recorded, and the material gathered through the interview session was transcribed. The audio recordings of the interviews were listened to several times to ensure accurate transcription.

Step 2: Searching for Similarities & Contradictions

This stage necessitates the identification of all data in the dataset that is relevant to the research questions. The phrase "searching for similarities and contradictions" encapsulates the heart of why you think a particular set of data could be useful. The researcher can use the manual coding technique to keep track of and interpret the many terms received. As a result, the data has been manually coded to make the task of finding similarities and discrepancies easier. The interviewee uses different words during the analysis of each transcript, yet they all clearly represent the same environment. The "Similarities" represent the thought or feeling stated in that section of the text. However, some respondents' perspectives opposed the similarities discovered; therefore, these were labeled as "contradictions".

Similarities & Contradictions:

Data points/ Codes	Similarities
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Finance• Financial Performance	<p>We go for VC to have financial support to expend our business as well as managerial expertise on other hand to compete in the market.....</p> <p>We are being allowed to work with a wide range of experts that assist us with every division of the business process, from marketing to scaling...</p> <p>Reason for opting VC is to get funded to scale our business....</p> <p>Regularly monitor our financial performance through their observations and different types of analysis.....</p> <p>A venture capital serves as a catalyst for a startup. It improves its financial position and managerial abilities.</p> <p>We chose venture capital to raise our funds and</p> <p>Venture investors, on the other hand, will demand a say in how you manage your company in exchange for their money.</p> <p>We got the opportunity to launch the financial wellbeing platform that is also a first one in its field.....</p> <p>With VC finance, your company will not only be able to expand easily, but it will also benefit from the investors' legal, financial, and business skills.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidance /Mentoring 	<p>It's their guidance and support therefore we are on perfect and right place having integration with telecommunication industry and collaboration with merchants like</p> <p>They have sat without accurate guidance and support which is provided by the VCs</p> <p>In this case I would acknowledge the mentorship provided by the partners.....</p> <p>They facilitate us like advisor. VC provides us with key guidance, critical infrastructure, and investment opportunities...</p> <p>VC has provided us the skills and expertise through different programs/activities/training sessions that.....</p> <p>Therefore we chose venture capital that is the only option to raise your funds along with mentorship and experience.</p> <p>VC also arranges management training programs to provide us the knowledge and skills that make us able to.....</p> <p>We know they have the strategies that have worked for other companies and have been proved but it may not work for.....</p> <p>..... notices our exercises month to month or quarterly then they exhort us shield our data, ensure all gear works appropriately.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Planning • New Idea & Strategies 	<p>It also helps us the planning and strategy to regarding obstacles while entering the market....</p> <p>We share our policies, plans, new opportunities with our partners then they guide or suggest us before implementing that plan or a policy.....</p> <p>They provide us skills that help us in execution, they have gone through what we are going through therefore they help in this regard too at tactical or strategic level management.</p> <p>we started a pilot program of three months. During pilot program our plan was to observe the problems.....</p> <p>VC assists us in various areas such as operational and strategic planning, supplier and personnel selection</p> <p>Ensure alternate plans are in place in the event of a failure, enable us to keep strong business to business relationships, having</p> <p>VC's help us building brand strategy, market research, developing brand identity and awareness.</p> <p>VC provide services that help us formulating, testing, or evaluating</p>

	<p>marketing plans, providing business contacts, most importantly engage with us during strategic planning</p> <p>.....external board of directors who monitor our activities and strategies to guide us effectively. The number of invention ideas that comes directly from management.</p> <p>VC guide us how to provide a customer with great satisfaction through our service, help us create.....</p> <p>.....we shares our arrangements, plans, and new freedoms with our accomplices then they direct or propose us prior to executing that arrangement or a strategy.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry Connections • Introduction to new customers & suppliers • Marketing& Networking 	<p>They have vast knowledge of the market, they guide us how we can bring our innovation to the people and market it</p> <p>Link with the industry through their support & guidance....</p> <p>Your first objective achieved but having industry connections through conferences and networking events helped us make it successful collaboration.....</p> <p>VC helps us create different strategies regarding market recognition of our service.</p> <p>You often gain access to an investor's network of contacts, as well as their business knowledge and experience.....</p> <p>VC mentions our services in different sessions and discussions on different platforms that really help us in the process of recognition of our services being provided.....</p> <p>To grow a concept into a successful company you need skills, network, expertise long with....</p> <p>VC have PR group and contacts in media, it's in their greatest advantage for your startup to gain visibility. Being linked can give a startup a lot of credibility..... Increased visibility can help you attract new skilled employees, valuable customers.</p> <p>VC introduces us with different industry channels that further create ease for reaching the target....</p> <p>Guide us appointing support staff. These support positions are filled by people with good knowledge of day-to-day operations.</p> <p>Their role in providing us the network with people and channels that also help us grow our business and new partnerships</p>

	<p>Introducing us some marketing connections that promote us on social media.....</p> <p>VC helps us in building different industry connections and relationships with different companies where we got support....</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management Expertise • Recruitment of staff & top management • Operations Planning 	<p>..... to expend our business as well as managerial expertise on other hand to compete in the market.</p> <p>Vcs are good at managing their operations and capturing market in short period of time or expected time.....</p> <p>Vcs guide us upon our operations and help us out in each problem that we face regarding.....</p> <p>They also help and guide us in recruitment process.</p> <p>To grow a concept into a successful company you need skills, network, expertise along with.....</p> <p>They provide business expertise as well. The new company's business activities will be assisted by a venture capitalist.</p> <p>They monitor us and add value the company by providing various managerial inputs, they have role in our decision making process.</p> <p>VC assists necessary they assume managerial roles by using their specific industrial knowledge, expertise, and contacts.</p> <p>.....and really need a mentorship and an expertise that can accelerate our company's growth.</p> <p>We have managed our operations properly and have adopted formal reporting structure, extensive due diligence</p> <p>Through due diligence with new regulations, legislations, market research that's how we manage to operate to lower the operational cost and lower chances of risk to happen.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Management • Crisis Management 	<p>Our partners observe our activities monthly or quarterly then they advise us safeguard our information; make sure all equipment works properly, ensure alternate plans are in place in the event of a failure....</p> <p>Our idea was risky in the perspective of political, economic, operational risk as well as market entry strategy risk. The selection of an inappropriate pricing, marketing, or distribution strategy is a large potential risk. Involvement of VC helped us in this regard by engaging experts' opinion and support.</p>

	<p>VC always keeps us updated with the risks such market, political, environmental and advise us to maintain strong</p> <p>.....we lose sight of the company trajectory and strategy. One person can't vanquish every risk..... and sound board that helped us in strategies to identify the directions to the market and where we can shape them effectively and mitigate the risk arose.</p> <p>Startup means surrounded by risks, financial risks, market risks, execution risks. Sharing risks and responsibilities bring ease in....</p> <p>VC guides us to avoid risks and lower operational costs by engaging us</p> <p>VC provides us the sound opinions upon the reports submitted by the risk monitoring teams.</p> <p>VC help us in the process of forecasting and improving methods and possibilities to lessen risks, to do this we always follow a strategy to mitigate risks, monitoring and planning, which</p> <p>Planning before the work then working on the obstacles and risk that you have identified during execution.</p> <p>VC help us to mitigate risks by making us operate according new strict policies and SOPs that consist of anticipated future risks and guidance how to be prepared in advance.....</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer Tastes & Preferences • Aligning the process • Current Market Trends 	<p>They let us go with the strategies that include how to create a need of our product</p> <p>They have guided us well about our target audience to recognize it and reach it.</p> <p>We need coach who already have vast area of expertise, skills, knowledge, he knows about market and how to run and secure a right place in the market that is a venture capital.</p> <p>We face regarding market understanding, market trend, human resource, and skills that we need to adopt to achieve.....</p> <p>We have research and development team that continuously observes market fluctuations and conditions....</p> <p>Focus on that experience, either market conditions will favor us or create obstacles; usually we get market experience....</p> <p>VC provides us with the guidance which helps us positioning our brand in mind of our target audience.</p> <p>VC's assistance us building brand procedure, statistical surveying, creating</p>

	<p>brand character and mindfulness. making local products available with premium and high quality, fair prices, trying to provide best customer experience.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of New Product • Development of Modified Product 	<p>Project comes with new features within that project modification occurs according to the market and customer..... are in charge of reshaping the industry, bringing new technology, coming with new ways in smart solutions</p> <p>.....we search for optimum solutions for that problem, by providing new or modified services that most in need.</p> <p>Bazaar was a new product in the field of B2B, B2C online services were available.....</p> <p>It was a new service ProCheck has established itself as the</p> <p>We got the opportunity to launch the financial wellbeing platform that is also a first one in its field.....</p> <p>The idea was previously available in the market of the other counties but it was not in the Pakistan in a certain formal way. We have introduced it in the Pakistan as a pioneer because.....</p>

Table: 1 Similarities found from the Interview Excerpts

<p><i>Contradictions</i></p>
<p>There are important roles played by the VC while decision making, but accepting finance means that business decisions will be determined, controlled and processed by the VC, which can be a significant shift for entrepreneurs who are comfortable to make their own decisions.</p>
<p>VC review our financial statements, make amendments in budgeting process, recommend us numerous sometimes painful workforce changes, bring major upgrades to our operational structure, sometimes recommend us to adapt to rigid compliance to a consistent set of key performance indicators and measurement tools across every department and every person. While involving in these types of functions and having compliance with KPIs we turned out to be lesser customer focus, we lost so many supportive and great leadership, disturbed our smooth operational structure. We wanted to have independent leadership and as supportive</p>
<p>VC funding is complicated, initially it's hard to get funds, you will have to invest countless efforts and time to showcase your company in front of powerful investors because funding process is very long and complicated as well as expensive & distracting. Despite, low chances of success if you succeeded you will</p>

have no control over your company independently. If you are a founder with no experience and expertise, VC may be a good source to be utilized, but your ownership will be divided as well.

VC is active in providing us management expertise but it's not a huge help on solving our company problems rather it create the environment that foster more problem to appear while solving those problems it require more efforts to accompany it.

Table: 2 Contradictions found from the Interview Excerpts

Step 3: Develop Codes

After finding the similarities from the interview transcripts we developed several codes from the interview excerpts. Total 17 codes have been developed and multiple codes from them were written in one row that gave almost same sense or referring to the similar concept. However, all the 17 codes are mentioned in Table no. # 01 with the similarities found.

Step 4: Generating Themes

First, the similarities and contradictions were meticulously researched in order to identify patterns and begin to develop themes. Based on the similarities observed in each respondent's transcripts, themes are frequently larger than data points or codes. It is now necessary to confirm that the identified themes accurately and productively represent the data. As a result, we took all of the similarities discovered in each respondent's transcripts and created themes based on the factors. At this point, it's possible to conclude that other themes exist that could be related to our objectives, other from the independent variables utilized in this study, and that they could be used as well. Some data points are extra; they may be relevant to our research topic but not very valuable for the objectives, thus they may become themes in and of themselves, telling something useful about the data. Some themes have been combined in light of the literature that offer the same meaning and depicts one concept as a whole.

Generating Themes

<u>Data Points / Codes</u>	<u>Themes</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finance • Monitoring Financial Performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finance
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidance/ Mentoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidance/ Mentoring
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry Connections • Introduction to new customers & suppliers • Marketing & Networking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry connections

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management Expertise • Recruitment of staff & top management • Operations Planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management Expertise
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Planning • New Ideas & Strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Planning & New Ideas
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Management • Crisis Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Mitigation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer tastes & preferences • Aligning the process • Current Market Trends 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research & Development
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of New Product • Development of Modified Product 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovating the Products

Table: 3 Generating Themes from the Codes Developed

Step 5: Results

In this section, the process is carried out to investigate the results of each thematic analysis method. The data was acquainted first, and the interviewee's responses were thoroughly read from the printed transcripts. Then there was the phase of looking for parallels and contrasts. Following the extraction of commonalities from the data, 8 themes that are pertinent to this research study are developed, namely:

- Finance
- Guidance/ Mentoring
- Industry connections
- Strategic Planning & New Ideas
- Management Expertise
- Risk Mitigation
- Research & Development
- Innovating the Products

Findings for the research question

Conceptual Framework Based On Findings:

ROLE OF VENTURE CAPITAL

Fig. 4: Conceptual Framework depicting the Role of Venture Capital

A. Role of venture capital in fostering innovation

It is previously reflected from the literature review that there are multiple essential factors to be addressed for that can contribute in spurring the innovation such as financial aid, guidance, formulating new strategies, risk management, developing industry connections, providing management expertise, monitoring the overall performance, aligning the process keeping the current market trends that results in the new product development or developing a modified or partially modified product. The innovation output results in innovating the products that depends on several factors or value added activities that venture capitalists would contribute.

The collected data clearly shows the currently successful position of the firm in the industry and the satisfactory views of the participants towards the performance and active involvement of their VC's. Following the study of the data gathered through interviews, thematic analysis was used to generate some data points. Following the study of the data gathered through interviews, thematic analysis was used to generate some data points. Table 1 shows the similarities and data points that were generated and shows that there are several factors integrated by VC's that contribute in the innovation outputs of a company. Referring to Table 3, where the themes of "Finance", "Guidance/ Mentoring", "Industry Connections", "Strategic Planning & New Ideas", "Management Expertise", Risk Mitigation", "Research & Development" and "Innovating the Products" have been generated, clearly shows that venture capital firms provide not only finance but several

other value added services that contributes in fostering innovation of the portfolio firm. So based on the data analysis and referring to Table 1 & 3, the research question of this study has been answered that the VC plays a significant and positive role in spurring innovation.

New product development is critical to an organization's success; nevertheless, while product development is critical, it is rarely gets effective for a variety of reasons. The first is lack of identification of the key characteristics that assist the product accelerate in the market. No matter how inventive the product is, if the success criteria are not identified, the product's success becomes more risky. It has an impact on product innovation, and no matter how much the product has the potential to be demanded in the market, it fails. Another cause of failure is that the processes are not sequenced. Sometimes, in order to boost sales, alignments and efficiency are overlooked, but this has a direct impact on the product's success. At first, it appears that the product is doing well, but owing to the organization's unplanned and chaotic procedures, it quickly goes into decline. Products that are not built with the target market in mind, as well as the taste and preferences of the customers, are doomed to fail. Launching a product that has little influence on efficiency or distinctiveness when compared to competitors can lead to failure. As being industry experts, here VC plays a vital role as depicted in Table 1 from the codes customer tastes & preferences, aligning the process, and current market trends.

The aspects addressed crucial for defining the role of venture capital in encouraging innovation for entrepreneurial startups are discussed in this study. The data collected informs about some valuable processes and non-financial value added services that emphasized the contribution and role of VC in spurring innovation. However, there is still room for more factors to influence the innovation process. A theme analysis technique is used to interpret the results and findings. Although there are several discrepancies as well as similarities in the transcripts, they demonstrate a common ground where all respondents have similar ideas. Those conflicting perspectives appear to be very valid, and the study was informed of the most important elements to remember in order to retain the components. Referring to table no 2, contradictions, for example, suggested that the new product may not be new to the user, but it may be new to the firm, and that the corporation must be prepared to deal with the ambiguity of the adopted strategies. Another opposing viewpoint is the changeable nature of consumer tastes and preferences, which is objectively observed as genuine and valid but which may be addressed by supporting product innovation over time. Also, another contradiction that business decisions will be determined controlled and processed by the VC, which can be a significant shift for entrepreneurs who are comfortable to make their own decisions. They start feeling a dire need of independent leadership, management and ownership. These contradictions reflect that the role of VC is somehow, dependent on the portfolio firms and after effects of market entry as well.

The conceptual framework created demonstrates the relevance of venture capitalists in encouraging innovation, as evidenced by the various themes generated in light of the research objectives. Thematic analysis was used to identify any similarities once the collected data from the interviews were analyzed. The commonalities and themes that emerged in Table 1 showed the role of VC in fostering innovation of the

entrepreneurial startups. Referring to section 4.2, Table 3, where the themes of “Finance”, “Guidance/ Mentoring”, “Industry Connections”, “Strategic Planning & New Ideas”, “Management Expertise”, Risk Mitigation”, “Research & Development” and “Innovating the Products” have been generated, clearly depicts that the VC plays a significant and positive role in spurring innovation.

5. Conclusion

The current study investigated the role of venture capital in spurring innovation for entrepreneurial startups or the impact of venture capital in the innovation process of new ventures. For that, the study gathered the data from 7 different venture backed portfolio companies of Karachi, Pakistan. A discussion session or interviews based on open-ended questions has been conducted and the gathered data has been analyzed through thematic analysis. In the analysis, total 17 codes have been generated from the similarities and contradictions extracted through the interview excerpts. The codes are later combined in the light of literature into 8 themes of “Finance”, “Guidance/ Mentoring”, “Industry Connections”, “Strategic Planning & New Ideas”, “Management Expertise”, Risk Mitigation”, “Research & Development” and “Innovating the Products”. In accordance with the literature the direct impact or role of venture capital has been investigated on innovation process of the portfolio firms.

As reflected from literature in section 2.5 that Venture capital has positive role in fostering innovation that VC funding enhances the scale of a company's inventive activity. Furthermore, Bernstein, Giroud & Townsend (2016) examine venture capitalists' involvement in fostering innovation within portfolio businesses. The most supported position, however, is that venture capital investors are "business builders" which both drive innovation and professionalization and marketing techniques. Based on Holmstrom & Tirole's double moral hazard model (1997) of venture capital, the theory underlines the active involvement of the venture capitalists as coaches and monitors of novice entrepreneurs (Baker & Gompers, 2003). In order to establish successful commercial operations, venture investors would consequently supply financing to teams of entrepreneurs as well as non-financial services such as monitoring, assistance and guidance.

However, we have interviewed around 7 different venture backed portfolio companies. After analysis, the data reflected almost 85% percent of positive and similar responses.

Fig. 5: Results of Interview Responses

So based on the data analysis and referring to Table 1 & 3, the research question of this study has been answered that the VC plays a significant and positive role in spurring innovation. VCs add value to the company, with capitalists playing a far more active role in helping businesses expand by providing additional competencies, contacts, expertise, and several more value-added services. Also, endorsed and concluded by several researchers that venture capital (VC) plays a demonstrable role in fostering innovation (Aizenman & Kendall 2012; Caselli, Gatti & Perrini 2009; Colombo, Dawid & Kabus 2012; Füss, & Schweizer 2012; Hasan & Wang 2006; Hirukawa & Ueda 2011; Keuschnigg, 2004; Popov & Roosenboom 2012; Zhang et al., 2013).

Limitation

The research is limited to the Karachi region of Pakistan. Many more industries exist in Pakistan, which are geographically dispersed and diverse in nature, and which have lower growth rates despite being venture-backed. The study's fundamental weakness is that it only considers one dimension. Furthermore, because this research is limited to Karachi, Pakistani startups, future research should focus on a different city, country, or industry. The data points and themes generated, on the other hand, provided prospects for further research into the topics discussed in Section 5.5. Whereas, in the future, new elements should be investigated affecting the innovation process or the inputs made by VC's should be explored other than the factors additionally identified in this study.

Recommendations

It's critical to be concerned that venture funding can also come with its consequences. Sometimes, it can increase stress on founders, pushing them into an unrelenting phase of development and creating bigger and bigger rounds to keep up. There are also possible issues if the connection between the founding team and the VC isn't good, meaning the latter can cause more problems than they solve. Due diligence both ways is vital to ensure that there is alignment on vision, goals, and ways of working.

It can be recommended that being a VC backed firm they have to work with teams and work within the right team. That team makes your start-up more potent, delivering the enormous quantity of work and leveraging the awareness, expertise, and experience of each team member, letting them to concentrate on doing no matter what it is they do best. Startups build with the right senior management team are those that are found right for accomplishment. Surviving with experienced team is less risky than surviving alone experiencing the new experiences. Also, it is recommended that venture capital firms should have to make sure that their services are going satisfactory by time and are time persistent as well. As the persistence of innovation is an essential element for any startup to successful survive in the long run.

Opportunities for further research

The research examined at how venture capitalists can help a new company innovate. The results and findings are interpreted using a theme analysis technique. The data points and themes gathered provided a thorough understanding of the research problem. Additional parallels, on the other hand, have become themes in and of themselves, telling something valuable for the goals of the research issue that is also related to the researched research issue but not to the aims and objectives. Referring to section 4.2, where the 8 themes have been generated and shows 3 additional themes that are relevant to the research objectives but haven't been explored properly. As indicated in table 3, the data points and themes generated additionally opened opportunities to further research on the factors such as:

- ❖ Strategic Planning & New Ideas
- ❖ Risk Mitigation
- ❖ Research & Development

As a result, the researcher may keep an eye out for these three factors discovered throughout the research's data analysis, as well as any other aspect that adds to the innovation process of venture-backed enterprises put in by their VCs. This approach could be used in future study, however innovation inputs from VCs should be viewed as a variable mediating component, and new factors affecting innovation output should be identified and examined.

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